

A. Supplementary Figures for the article: *Spatial clustering of front yard landscapes: implications for urban soil conservation and green infrastructure sustainability in the Río Piedras Watershed* by L. K. Sellés and E. J. Meléndez-Ackerman published in *Sustainability*

Figure S1 Scatter plots and Spearman correlation analyses to evaluate the level of association of all the evaluated variables. Asterisks indicate significant correlation coefficients at $p < 0.05$ (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

Figure S2 Contribution of the three components for the Front Yard Quality Index (FYQI).

Image obtained from Google Earth Pro. Imagery: U.S. Geological Survey. Map data © Google.

Image obtained from Google Earth Pro. Imagery © 2025 Maxar Technologies. Map data © Google.

Figure S3 Aerial images focusing on sidewalk changes in Puerto Nuevo. Two images show different dates: a) before the sidewalk reconstruction in 2006 and b) after the reconstruction in 2016.

B. Supplementary Tables for the article: *Spatial clustering of front yard landscapes: implications for urban soil conservation and green infrastructure sustainability in the Río Piedras Watershed* by L. K. Sellés and E. J. Meléndez-Ackerman published in *Sustainability*

Table S1 Approximate Construction Dates for 17 Urban Developments studied in the article:

Approximate construction dates for all the urban developments evaluated in this study. Urbanized areas in San Juan by 1974 include:

- Venezuela (“informal development” constructed before 1920)
- Buen Consejo (“informal development” constructed before 1920)
- Puerto Nuevo (1941 – 1950)
- Roosevelt (1941 – 1950)
- Baldrich (1941 – 1950)
- San Patricio (1951 – 1960)
- Caparra Terrace (1951 – 1960)
- Las Lomas (1951 – 1960)
- Reparto Metropolitano (1951 – 1960)
- Iglesias Patín (1951 – 1960)
- Altamesa (1951 – 1960)
- La Riviera (1951 – 1960)
- Las Américas (1951 – 1960)
- University Gardens (1920 – 1960)
- Jardines Metropolitanos (1951 – 1960)
- Villa Nevarez (1951 – 1960)
- La Experimental (1951 – 1960)

Source: Rodriguez Colon, S.R. *Impacto de Las Leyes de Planificación en el Crecimiento y Desarrollo del Área Metropolitana de San Juan*; Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Puerto Rico, Río Piedras: San Juan, Puerto Rico, 1975.

Table S2 Newspaper Articles with details of original design, prices and amenities for houses. Compilation of promotions and newspaper articles illustrating information of lot sizes and housing amenities. These newspapers were accessed through two digital archives *El Imparcial* (<https://gpa.eastview.com/eida/>) and *El Mundo* (<https://gpa.eastview.com/crl/elmundo/>) newspapers. All references are in Table S2.5

Table S2.1 Housing Prices Reported in Advertisements

Prices of “low-cost” houses in:

- Puerto Nuevo (\$4,600) [1]
- Reparto Metropolitano (\$6,000) [2]
- Las Lomas (\$6,000) [3]
- Caparra Terrace (\$6,500) [4]

Prices and amenities of higher-cost houses in:

- University Gardens (\$15,500 - 22,700) [5]
- Las Americas (price not specified) [6]
- Caparra Heights (\$10,200 - \$10,700) [7]
- Jardines Metropolitanos (\$14,275) [8]
- Villa Nevarez (\$8,000 - \$10,000) [3]

Table S2.2 Summary of advertisements related to housing sales in urban developments in the lower Río Piedras Watershed, San Juan, Puerto Rico published between 1950 and 1974.

- Advertisement by Long Construction Company (in charge of the construction in Puerto Nuevo and other neighborhoods) was motivated by the aspiration of moving from informal housing (“arrabales”) to organized housing projects (“urbanizaciones”) [9]
- Advertisement aimed at US veterans. Houses for sale in the Puerto Nuevo “massive” urban development. The newspaper ad states that these houses have a lot area of 250 m². The ad contains an image that shows an example of the magnitude of the project and the configuration of houses [10]
- Advertisement aimed at civilians. Another ad for houses for sale in Puerto Nuevo but stating that houses are also available for all residents in Puerto Rico [11].

- Advertisement for Puerto Nuevo published by Long Construction Company which describes the project to the public. Aerial images show the extent of massive urban development and provide examples of completed units [12]
- Advertisement for other projects of Long Homes (Directly related to the Long Construction Company). Here they are advertising new houses in Caparra Terrace with an example of the duplex house model used [4].
- Advertisement for the Jardines Metropolitanos urban development. Images show the models available for this development. The Ad shows both the company in charge of the construction: "Constructora de Puerto Rico, Inc" and the corporation in charge of sales: "Hogares Metropolitanos". Prices for these houses started at \$14,275 [8].
- Advertisement for the inauguration of University Gardens urban development. Images show examples of the various models in construction and the construction processes, which were in charge of "Hormigonera de Puerto Rico, Inc". This development had 13 models in total [13]
- Advertisement for Las Americas urban development in which they highlight the various amenities of the houses. Images show the sole housing model for the project and the location of the project. For this urban development, the company in charge of the construction was "Fullana Corporation" [6]
- Advertisement for the Caparra Heights urban development which highlights the convenient location of the project and the price range of the properties: \$8,250 - \$10,500. There are several images of the finished project with houses showing the extension of their front yards. For this urban development, the company in charge of the construction was "Borinquen Home Corporation" [14]
- Advertisement for the Reparto Metropolitano "massive" urban development (1,800 houses) showing various examples of houses. For this urban development, the company in charge of the construction was "Fullana Corporation" [15]
- Advertisement for University Gardens urban development listing the 13 house models buyers could choose from. The price range for these houses was \$15,500 - \$22,700 [16]
- Advertisement for the University Gardens urban development listing the 13 house models buyers could choose from. The price range for these houses was \$15,500 - \$22,700. The ad contains an image of one of the original models of the houses showing the extension of the front yard [5]

Table S2.3 List of advertisements that were found to show images of original housing unit designs showing front yards for the urban developments in the northern region of the Rio Piedras Watershed

- Puerto Nuevo [9]
- Caparra Terrace [17]
- Reparto Metropolitano [18]
- Roosevelt [19]
- Las Lomas [20]
- University Gardens [16]
- Caparra Heights [21]

Table S2.4 References for Ads related to housing sales between 1950 and 1975. Digital archives accessed: *El Imparcial* (<https://gpa.eastview.com/eida/>) and *El Mundo* (<https://gpa.eastview.com/crl/elmundo/>).

1. Anuncios Clasificados. *El Imparcial* 1948, 29.
2. Casas Baratas. *El Mundo* 1954, 6.
3. También Caparra. Ponen Nombre Piñero Barrio Puerto Nuevo. *El Mundo* 1955, 22.
4. Razones Por La Que Debe Ud. Comprar Una "duplex". *El Imparcial* 1952, 4.
5. Usted También Se Enamorará... de University Gardens! *El Imparcial* 1959, 22.
6. Esta Es La Primera Urbanización Que Le Ofrece Toda Su Casa Con Aire Acondicionado. *El Imparcial* 1958, 37.
7. Casas En Caparra Heights. *El Imparcial* 1948, 34.
8. Presentando Jardines Metropolitanos. *El Imparcial* 1960, 11.
9. El Mundo . *El Mundo* 1951, 16.
10. Puerto Nuevo La Urbanización Mas Grande Del Mundo. *El Mundo* 1949, 11.
11. Esto Es Una Buena Noticia Para Los Civiles. *El Mundo* 1949, 13.
12. ¡Felicitamos a Puerto Nuevo En El Día de Su Santo...! *El Mundo* 1951, 11.
13. Construyendo Mejor! Y Con Mayor Confianza! *El Imparcial* 1959, 45.
14. Caparra Heights - Una Nueva Ciudad de 1,000 Casas. *El Mundo* 1947, 13.
15. Las Empresas Fullana Se Enorgullecen En Presentar al Pueblo de Puerto Rico Sus Casas Modelos En El Moderno Reparto Metropolitano. *El Mundo* 1954, 3.
16. University Gardens. *El Imparcial* 1959, 31.
17. El Mundo Nunca Antes y Nunca Mas Se Ofreceran En Puerto Rico Casas Tan Excepcionales y Condiciones de Venta Tan Liberales. *El Mundo* 1952, 16.
18. El Mundo Las Emperas Fullana Se Enorgullecen En Presentar al Pueblo de Puerto Rico Sus Casas Modelos En El Moderno Reparto Metropolitano. *El Mundo* 1954, 13.
19. AACUPR Urbanizacion Roosevelt. *Colección Puerto Rico Reconstruction Administration (PRRA)* 1937.
20. Arroyo, M. Surge Una Nueva Ciudad de 100,000 Habitantes. *El Imparcial* 1955, 2-4.
21. Casas En "Caparra Heights." *El Mundo* 1948, 4.